

Spectroscopic and physicochemical studies on the charge transfer complex of dextromethorphan drug with iodine

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Abstract : The drug dextromethorphan had been shown to form a charge transfer (CT) complex of 1 : 1 stoichiometry with iodine in different solvents. The enthalpy and entropy of formation of this complex had been determined by estimating the formation constant spectrophotometrically at three different temperatures. The solvent variation study on the intermolecular CT complex formation revealed that the intensity of the interaction increases with decrease in relative permittivity of the medium. Transition energy, oscillator strength and dipole moments of the complex as well as the ionization potential of the donor have been computed from spectroscopic data and discussed. The experimentally measured ionization potential of the donor drug closely agrees with that computed theoretically using MOPAC (PM3) semi-empirical method.

Keywords : Charge transfer complex, dextromethorphan, iodine, solvent effect.

Introduction

Charge transfer (CT) complexes play an essential role in various fields such as analysis of drugs in pure form or pharmaceutical preparations^{1,2}, solar energy storage³ and surface chemistry⁴ as well as in many biological fields⁵. The mechanism of action of a drug is largely determined by its physicochemical properties in solution. Thus, spectroscopic and thermodynamic studies of drug molecules are of great relevance in pharmacokinetics⁶. On the other hand, spectroscopic and thermodynamic investigations not only serve these purposes but also lead to a measure of the strength of binding of the drug molecules to other substances present in living systems⁷. CT complexes are also known to take part in many chemical reactions like addition, substitution and condensation^{8,9}.

Iodine is well-known for its electron-accepting properties, which may be deduced from molecular orbital consideration. In human biology, iodine is required for the biosynthesis of the thyroid hormones triiodothyronine and thyroxine, which is involved in human thyroid metabolism. The spectroscopic and thermodynamic properties of the CT-complex of iodine with electron donors have been extensively studied¹⁰⁻²⁰. Some of the CT-complexes of iodine show interesting physical properties such as electrical conductivities²¹ and some of the complexes have

found applications in many forms of electronics and solar cells²² and some are used for determination of drugs²³.

The present work deals with the study of CT-complex formation between dextromethorphan (an anti-tissue agent) drug and the biologically significant iodine acceptor in different solvents using UV-visible spectroscopy. The spectral characteristics of the CT-bands, the equilibrium and thermodynamic parameters of the formed CT-complex are evaluated and discussed.

Results and discussion

Spectral characteristics of the CT-bands : The electronic absorption spectra of the CT-complex of the dextromethorphan-iodine system was recorded using constant acceptor concentration (in a given solvent), while the concentration of the donor was varied within the range from 2.240×10^{-3} to 60.605×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, depending on the solvent, but always $[D] \gg [A]$. The absorption spectra of mixed donor-acceptor solutions were characterized by the appearance of a new absorption band. This new absorption band was attributed to the formation of CT-complex and this complex is stable under the studied conditions. A representative spectrum in chloroform at 298 K is shown in Fig. 1. All the spectra of the mix-

Fig. 1. Electronic absorption spectra of dextromethorphan (D), iodine (A) and dextromethorphan-iodine complex (C) in chloroform at 298 K : [D] = $6.9087 \times 10^{-3} M$; [A] = $9.8499 \times 10^{-5} M$.

tures containing the acceptor and donor were recorded against the corresponding acceptor as reference.

It should be noted that dextromethorphan drug exhibited practically no absorption within the wavelength range where the CT-complex exhibits absorption. It was evident that upon the addition of dextromethorphan solution to iodine solution the absorption band at 500 nm which is attributed to the $4\pi \rightarrow 10\sigma^*$ electronic transition in free iodine is hypsochromically shifted due to its complexation with the added dextromethorphan drug. The observed hypsochromic shift in the free iodine band could be attributed to the perturbation of the iodine molecular orbital $10\sigma^*$ by a repulsive interaction between the complex. Accordingly, a more repulsive interaction would lead to a large blue shift of the iodine band. Therefore, it is reasonable to consider that extent of the blue shift in

the iodine band as a measure of the magnitude of interaction between the donor and iodine molecule^{10,11,20}. Hence, in the present system, in all the solvents studied, the hypsochromic shift to a larger extent indicated a stronger interaction between the drug and the acceptor molecule. The intensities of such spectra are time-independent where no observable variations were detected with time. The wavelength, CT-energy, frequency and wave number corresponding to the absorption maxima of the complex in different solvents are given in Table 1.

Stoichiometry of the CT-complex : The stoichiometry of the CT-complex was determined by applying Job's method²⁴. The symmetrical curve with maximum at 0.5 mole fraction indicate the formation of 1 : 1 CT-complex in all the solvents studied and a representative plot is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Job's continuous variation method for the CT complex of dextromethorphan with iodine (322 nm) in *iso*-propyl alcohol at 298 K.

Table 1. Spectral properties and absorption maxima of dextromethorphan-iodine CT-complex in different solvents

Solvent	λ_{max} (nm)	$h\nu_{CT}$ (eV)	$10^{14} \nu_{max}$ (s ⁻¹)	$\bar{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹)	$\Delta\nu_{1/2}$	f	μ	b^2/a^2	I_p (eV)	W (eV)
Chloroform	431	2.88	6.96	23202	6175	0.012	1.054	0.37	7.29	1.71
1,2-Dichloroethane	320	3.88	9.38	31250	3637	0.019	1.149	0.17	8.81	2.24
<i>iso</i> -Butyl alcohol	423	2.93	7.09	23641	3939	0.006	0.726	0.34	7.37	1.74
<i>iso</i> -Propyl alcohol	322	3.85	9.32	31056	4290	0.169	3.403	0.34	8.77	2.22
Methanol	314	3.95	9.55	31847	7143	0.188	3.539	0.34	8.92	2.27
Acetonitrile	420	2.95	7.14	23810	6092	0.006	0.707	0.24	7.40	1.75

Formation constant and molar extinction coefficients of the CT-complex : The formation constant (K) and molar extinction coefficients (ϵ) of the CT-complex studied have been determined using the following Scott equation²⁵,

$$[D][A]/d = [D]/\epsilon + 1/K\epsilon \quad (1)$$

where $[D]$ and $[A]$ are the initial molar concentration of the donor and acceptor, respectively and d is the absorbance. The values of K and ϵ were determined from the gradient and intercept of the linear plot of $[D][A]/d$ against $[D]$ (Fig. 3). The values of formation constant and molar extinction coefficient obtained at different temperature in

Fig. 3. Scott linear plot for dextromethorphan-iodine complex in different solvents at 298 K.

all the solvents studied are listed in Table 2 along with the relative permittivity of the solvents. The results indicated that the molar extinction coefficient, in general, increases as the strength of the donor-acceptor interaction increases as expected. The high values of K reflects high stabilities of the formed CT-complex^{10,26}.

The observed decrease in the formation constant values with rise in temperature indicates the exothermic nature of the interaction between the studied acceptor and donor molecules. Further there was a good correlation ($r = 0.94$) between the formation constant and relative permittivity of the medium (Fig. 4) indicating that the formation of the CT-complex was solvent dependent and increased with a decrease in relative permittivity of the medium.

Thermodynamic parameters of the CT-complex : The

Table 2. Formation constant (K , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) and the molar extinction coefficient (ϵ , $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) for the dextromethorphan-iodine CT-complex as a function of relative permittivity (ϵ_r) of the solvent and temperature (T , Kelvin)

Solvent	ϵ_r	T	K	ϵ
Chloroform	4.90	298	3567	455
		305	1204	556
		313	494	667
1,2-Dichloroethane	10.36	298	3757	1236
		305	3077	1035
		313	1745	1094
<i>iso</i> -Butyl alcohol	20.70	298	1341	345
		305	513	370
		313	144	435
<i>iso</i> -Propyl alcohol	32.7	298	849	9132
		305	811	8804
		313	809	8987
Methanol	36.71	298	667	6085
		305	519	6631
		313	389	6382
Acetonitrile	37.5	298	878	213
		305	439	232
		313	178	175

Fig. 4. Effect of relative permittivity of the medium on the formation constant of dextromethorphan-iodine CT-complex at 298 K.

thermodynamic parameters viz. Gibb's free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes were evaluated from the temperature dependence of the formation constant using the van't Hoff plots (not shown). The parameters thus ob-

tained are collected in Table 3. The negative free energy change indicated that the complexation is thermodynamically favoured. The negative enthalpy change revealed

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters of dextromethorphan-iodine CT-complex in different solvents

Solvent	$-\Delta H^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^\circ$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Chloroform	86.2	222.0	20.0
1,2-Dichloroethane	39.9	64.8	20.5
<i>iso</i> -Butyl alcohol	115.6	327.7	17.9
<i>iso</i> -Propyl alcohol	117.5	335.3	17.6
Methanol	27.8	39.2	16.1
Acetonitrile	82.4	219.9	16.8

that the CT-complex formation between the used donor and the acceptor is of exothermic in nature. The values of ΔH° and ΔS° generally become more negative as the stability constant for molecular complexes increases. As the binding between donor and acceptor becomes stronger, ΔH° would be expected to have higher negative values. The negative values of ΔH° are a pointer to the strength of the binding between drug and iodine, and the high stability of the resultant CT-complex. As the bond between the components becomes stronger and thus the components are subjected to more physical strain or loss of freedom, the values of ΔH° and ΔS° should be more negative. Hence a linear correlation between ΔH° and ΔS° should be observed²⁷. In the present study, such a linear correlation ($r = 0.999$, Fig. 5) was found to exist

Fig. 5. Relation between enthalpy and entropy of activation for the interaction of dextromethorphan with iodine.

for the dextromethorphan-iodine CT-complex in different solvents indicating the formation of a strong CT-complex²⁸.

Spectral properties of the CT-complex : The experimental oscillator strength (f) and the transition dipole moment (μ) of the CT-complex were calculated using the following approximate formula²⁶,

$$f = 4.32 \times 10^{-9} [\epsilon_{\max} \Delta\nu_{1/2}] \quad (2)$$

$$\mu = 0.0958 [\epsilon_{\max} \Delta\nu_{1/2} / \bar{\nu}_{\max}]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ is the band with half intensity, ϵ_{\max} and $\bar{\nu}_{\max}$ the molar extinction coefficient and wave number at the absorption maximum of the complex, respectively. The $\Delta\nu_{1/2}$, f and μ values computed are also reported in Table 1. The values of the calculated oscillator strength are rather relatively large indicating a strong interaction between the donor-acceptor pair with relative high probabilities of CT transitions²⁶.

According to Mullikens theory²⁹, the wave function of the ground state ψ_N of the molecular complex DA can be written as :

$$\psi_N = a\psi_0(D, A) + b\psi_1(D^+ - A^-) \quad (4)$$

where ψ_0 refers to the non-bond wave function and ψ_1 corresponds to the dative bond wave function. The ratio b^2/a^2 between the coefficient of the dative structure to the non-bond structure wave functions ($\psi_{D^+A^-}$ and ψ_{DA} , respectively) was calculated. The obtained ratio (Table 1) is comparable to that of many strong CT-complexes^{11,30,31}. This substantiates the strong nature inferred for the formed dextromethorphan-iodine CT-complex.

Ionization potential of the donor : Out of the many applications of the CT-complexes, one important application is to calculate the ionization potential of the donor. The ionization potential (I_p) of the highest filled molecular orbital of the donor was estimated from CT energies of the CT-band making use of the following relationship^{13,32},

$$I_p \text{ (eV)} = 2.9 + 1.89 \times 10^{-4} \bar{\nu}_{\text{iodine}} \text{ cm}^{-1} \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{\nu}$ is the wave number corresponding to the CT-band of the CT-complex. The values of ionization potentials thus determined in different solvents are given in Table 1. The average ionization potential of the donor was found to be 8.24 eV. It is interesting to note that the experimentally measured ionization potential is in fairly good agreement with that (8.98 eV) computed theoretically using MOPAC (PM3) method.

Further evidence for the nature of CT-interaction in the present systems is the calculation of the dissociation energy (W) of the CT excited state of the complex in

different solvents. The dissociation energy of the complex was calculated from the CT-energy, $h\nu_{CT}$, the ionization potential of the donor, I_p and electron affinity, E^A , of the acceptor using the empirical relation³³ given in eq. (6),

$$h\nu_{CT} = I_p - E^A - W \quad (6)$$

The calculated values of W are also given in Table 1. The values of the dissociation energy of the CT excited states of the complex in different solvents were constant, which suggested that the investigated complex is reasonably strong and stable under the studied conditions with higher resonance stabilization energy^{26,34}.

Conclusion : It may be concluded that iodine forms a strong CT-complex of 1 : 1 stoichiometry with the dextromethorphan drug in all the solvents studied.

The formation constant of the CT-complex was found to be highly solvent dependent. The investigated complex was stable and exothermic in nature. From the trends in the CT-absorption bands, the ionization potential of the drug molecule had been estimated. The ionization potential of the drug molecule and the heat of complexation data, in several media, may be useful in understanding the binding of the drug molecule in real pharmacokinetic study.

Experimental

All the solvents used were of spectroscopic grade. The electron donor drug dextromethorphan was obtained as gift samples from locally available pharmaceutical company and was used as received. The acceptor iodine was obtained from Aldrich, India. The selection of the solvents was based on the solubility of the donor and acceptor molecules and such a way to have a wide range of relative permittivity values. The electronic absorption spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu (UV 240, Graphicord) double beam spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched quartz cells. The temperature of the cell holder was controlled with a water flow. All absorbance measurements were

performed by using freshly prepared solutions. Theoretical calculation of the ionization potential of the donor was performed as reported earlier²⁶.

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References

1. S. Sadeghi and E. Karimi, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 2006, **54**, 1107.
2. I. A. Darwish, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2005, **549**, 212.
3. H. Kusama and H. Sugihara, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. A-Chem.*, 2006, **181**, 268.
4. S. M. Andrade, S. M. B. Costa and R. Pansu, *J. Colloid. Interf. Sci.*, 2000, **226**, 260.
5. K. Bradley, M. Briman, A. Star and G. Gruner, *Nano Lett.*, 2004, **4**, 253.
6. P. Toboada, M. Gutierrez-Pichel, S. Barbosa, D. Attwood and V. Mosquera, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2003, **5**, 703.
7. N. E. Weob and C. C. Thompson, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1978, **67**, 165.
8. O. Van Den Berg, W. F. Jager and S. J. Picken, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2006, **71**, 2666.
9. T. Roy, K. Dutta, M. K. Nayek, A. K. Mukherjee, M. Banerjee and B. K. Seal, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 2000, 531.
10. A. A. Ibrahim, *Microchemical J.*, 1998, **58**, 175.
11. E. H. El-Mossalamy, A. S. Amin and A. A. Khalil, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2002, **58**, 67.
12. Kh. A. Hassan, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 3059.
13. H. M. A. Salman, M. M. Abu-Krishna and H. S. El-Sheshtawy, *Can. J. Anal. Sci. Spectros.*, 2004, **49**, 282.
14. E. M. El-Nemma, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 3181.
15. N. A. Al-Hashimi, K. A. Hassan and El-Metwally Nour, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2005, **62**, 317.
16. L. A. Shahada, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2005, **61**, 1795.
17. M. Hasani and A. Rezaei, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2006, **65**, 1093.
18. T. M. El-Gogary, M. A. Diab and S. F. El-Tantawy, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2007, **66**, 94.
19. M. Hasani and S. Akbari, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2007, **68**, 409.

20. U. M. Rabie, R. A. Mohamed and M. H. Abou-El-Wafa, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2007, **68**, 605.
21. P. J. Trotter and P. A. White, *Appl. Spectrosc.*, 1978, **32**, 232.
22. N. A. Al-Hashimi, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 2181.
23. L. I. Bebamik, K. El-Kelani, L. Abdel Fattah and A. S. Ahmed, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1997, **86**, 1030.
24. P. Job, *Ann. Chim. Phys.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
25. R. L. Scott, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas Belg.*, 1956, **75**, 787.
26. M. Pandeeswaran and K. P. Elango, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2006, **65**, 1148.
27. D. M. Ford, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 16167.
28. G. M. Neelgund and M. L. Budni, *Monatshefte fur Chemie*, 2004, **135**, 1395.
29. R. S. Mulliken, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 811.
30. R. Abu-Eittah and M. M. Hamed, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1979, **57**, 2337.
31. A. A. M. Belal and L. H. Abdel-Rahman, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 1999, **55**, 2745.
32. G. G. Aloisi and S. Pignataro, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1973, **69**, 534.
33. H. McConnel, J. S. Ham and J. R. Platt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, **21**, 66.
34. M. Pandeeswaran and K. P. Elango, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 399.